

Bridging ethnomedicine and modern science: The phytopharmacological journey of *Solanum torvum*

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ABSTRACT

Majority of the pharmaceuticals available today have their origins in plants either directly or indirectly. *Solanum torvum* Swartz, a member of the Solanaceae family, is a globally dispersed medicinal herbal plant. This review aims to highlight the correlation between the various phytochemicals possessed by *S. torvum* and their pharmacological implications. A literature search was conducted using various online resources including PUBMED, Google scholar and Science Direct. Due to its abundant phytochemical content, it is utilised in the treatment of a wide range of ailments. In traditional medicine system all over the globe, it is used as a medication against diabetes, hypertension, inflammation, microbial infections, cytotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, immunological disorders and ulcer. The insights gained from this review should improve our understanding of the health benefits of *S. torvum* and its related phytochemicals, which could pave the way for new pharmaceuticals to treat and prevent diseases.

Key Words - *Solanum torvum*, ethnomedicine, phytopharmacological journey, phytochemical

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INTRODUCTION

Natural remedies have been an integral part of traditional medicine practices for thousands of years. Natural therapies tend to have more support from those who believe in their efficacy and safety compared to pharmaceuticals. Plants typically possess therapeutic effects because of phytochemicals, thousands of which have been identified and studied or because of the presence of basic chemical elements like selenium or chromium in plant tissues.

There are over 3000 species and 90 genera in the Solanaceae family, which are extensively scattered throughout the world. They are a great source of active secondary metabolites (Silva *et al.*, 2004). *Solanum torvum* Swartz, often known as Sundakai (Tamil), Makhua phuang (Thai), Thibbatu (Sinhala),

Turkey Berry and Wild Eggplant is a member of the Solanaceae family (Ramamurthy *et al.*, 2012). Among the many phytochemical components found in plant extract of *S. torvum* are steroids, glycosides, saponins, flavonoids, phenols, vitamins C and E, iron salt and steroidal alkaloids (Jaiswal, 2012; Thenmozhi & US, 2012). Some phytochemicals are harmless whereas others are harmful. Most of them have anti-cancer, antibacterial, antiviral antioxidant, antidiarrheal, analgesic and anti-inflammatory, immuno-secretory, nephroprotective, antidiabetic, cardiovascular and wound-healing properties (Ajaiyeoba, 1999; Arthan *et al.*, 2002; Chah *et al.*, 2000; Gandhi, Ignacimuthu, Paulraj, *et al.*, 2011; Israf *et al.*, 2004; Mohan *et al.*, 2010; Sivapriya & Leela, 2007a). As a whole the plant has

long been used for its digestive, diuretic and sedative properties; however, decoctions made from its fruits and leaves have long been used to alleviate coughing and enlarged liver and spleen (Kala, 2005; Siemonsma & Piluek, 1994).

1. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS

The spiny shrub of *S. torvum* grows to a height of 2-3 meters (Figure 1). The leaves are oval or elliptical in form and have a shallow indentation that tapers to an acute to obtuse tip. The shrub also bears fruits or berries which are small and spherical in shape (Figure 3) and white bell-shaped flowers

(Figure 2). The fruits are green when young and turn yellow when ripe (Jaiswal, 2012; Ogwu *et al.*, 2024). *S. torvum* can either be annual or perennial, depending on the circumstances. Plants thrive in full sunlight, mild shade or partial shade but not under a forest canopy (Little *et al.*, 1974). *S. torvum* fruits are widely available, edible and are used as a vegetable. They are also an important part of the traditional South Indian diet (Sivapriya & Leela, 2007a). In the tropics, the shrub is grown for its acrid immature fruits. It has been identified to be grown in the west Indies (Adjanohoun *et al.*, 1996).

Fig. 1: Plant of *Solanum torvum* Sw.

Fig. 2: Flowers of *Solanum torvum* Sw.

Fig. 3: Fruits of *Solanum torvum* Sw.

2. PHYTOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Phytochemicals are secondary metabolites produced by plant cells that fulfil the roles beyond the primary requirements of the cell, thereby aiding in the overall survival of the plant as a functional organism. The characteristic properties of phytochemicals allow us to identify the distinct biological activities of plants. *Solanum torvum* has been reported to possess phytochemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, carbohydrates, steroids, glycosides, proteins and amino acids (Chah *et al.*, 2000; Kalita *et al.*, 2017). Polyphenolic compounds such as phenol (160.30 mg/g), flavonoid (104.36 mg/g) and tannin (65.91 mg/g) were identified by (Kusirisin *et al.*, 2009a). Mc *et al.* (2007) also concluded that *S. torvum* had

a total alkaloid content (0.12%), total glycoalkaloids (0.038%) and glycosylated compounds derived from solasodine, namely solasonine (0.0043%) and solamargine (0.0028%).

Phytochemical study revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, glycosides, oils, tocopherols (Vitamins E, B and C) and iron salts in the methanolic extracts of sun dried *S. torvum* (Amarowicz *et al.*, 2010; Koffuor *et al.*, 2011a; Sivapriya & Leela, 2007b). The Indian-native *S. torvum* leaf extract contained nine (Triacontanol, Octacosanyl triacontanoate, 5-hexatriacontanone, 3-triacontanoate, Tetratriacontanoic acid, Sitosterol, Stigmasterol, Campesterol, 2,3,4-trimethyltriacontane) non-alkaloid chemical compounds (Mahmood *et al.*, 1983). Along with the

well-known glycoside; torviside A, (Arthan *et al.*, 2002) discovered a new isoflavonoid sulphate called torvanol A and a new steroidal glycoside called torviside H in fruit methanolic extracts. The nine novel compounds identified by (Y.-Y. Lu *et al.*, 2011) include neochlorogenin 6-O- β -D-quinovopyranoside, neochlorogenin 6-O- β -D-xylopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-quinovopyranoside, neochlorogenin 6-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-quinovopyranoside, solagenin 6-O- α -D-quinovopyranoside, solagenin 6-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-quinovopyranoside, isoquercetin, rutin, kaempferol and quercetin (Lakshmi *et al.*, 2013) reported the notable absence of anthraquinones and cyanides in the methanol, petroleum and chloroform extracts derived from the fruits, leaves and roots of *S. torvum*. Additionally, it was unexpectedly noted that glycosides and flavonoids were also absent. The ethanolic extract of the aerial portions of *S. torvum* yielded two new C-22 steroidal lactone saponins that are solanolactosides A and solanolactosides B, as well as two new spirostanol glycosides which are torvisides M and torvisides N (Y. Lu *et al.*, 2009). The presence of Furostanol glycoside 26-O- β -glucosidase was identified as a significant component within the methanolic extracts of leaves (Iida *et al.*, 2005).

3. ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

Antioxidants are crucial for preventing lipid peroxidation or preventing free radicals from damaging cells. When compared to well-known traditional synthetic antioxidants, the novel protein obtained from the aqueous extract of Sundakai seed has been found to be a potent antioxidant, even at low doses (Sivapriya & Leela, 2007a). Antioxidant activity index results showed that 3.68 mg Trolox and 360.53 mg of ascorbic acid equivalents were detected in one gram of concentrated *S. torvum* extract. The phenolic and flavonoid content of *S. torvum* has been found to have inhibitory effects on the CYP2E1 enzyme and free radical scavenging capabilities, particularly in relation to the lipid peroxidation and superoxide anion activity (Kusirisin *et al.*, 2009b).

Table 1: Phytochemicals and their therapeutic effects

Sl. No.	Phytochemicals	Therapeutics
1	Alkaloids	a. Defend the body from oxidative stress b. Chemotherapeutic treatment. c. Used as chemo preventive agents. d. Limit, stop or slow the growth of tumour.
2	Flavonoids	a. Avoiding heart related illnesses. b. Exhibit anti-ulcer characteristics.
3	Tannins	a. Prevention of heart-related disease. b. Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects. c. Reduce and sustain the diastolic and systolic blood pressure.
4	Glycosides	a. Nutritive purposes. b. Effective for cough ailments. c. Treatment of liver and spleen enlargement
5	Tocopherols/ Vitamin E	a. Sustain metabolism and boost immune system. b. Inhibit the formation of carcinogens in the stomach. c. Prevent the growth of cataracts in the eyes.
6	Phenols	a. Lower blood cholesterol. b. Prevention of breast, colon and prostate cancers c. Used in cancer therapy.
7	Oils	a. Optimal performance of the brain, b. Regulate reproductive function c. Enhance bone health. d. Treatment of pains associated with rheumatoid arthritis e. Dermatology disease therapy.
8	Vitamin C	a. Keeps the body against oxidative stress.

S. torvum exhibits extensive antioxidant properties, suggesting its potential application in the avoidance or therapy of Neurodegenerative diseases (Mohan *et al.*, 2017). Natural antioxidants derived from plants, including vitamin C and E, carotenes, phenolics, flavonoids, phytates and phytoestrogens are thought to disrupt the oxidation process by interacting with the free radicals, chelating catalytic metals and scavenging oxygen within biological systems (Boham & Kocipai-Abyazan, 1974; Prasad *et al.*, 2010). *S. torvum* demonstrated certain antioxidant properties and the potential to repair DNA damage induced by free radicals (Abas *et al.*, 2006). A balance between oxidation and antioxidant level is essential for maintaining healthy biological integrity (Young & Woodside, 2001).

At an oral dosage of 100 mg/kg, the methanolic extract of seeds from *S. torvum* demonstrated promising antioxidative and antidiabetic effects (Mohan *et al.*, 2020).

4. ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

The species *S. torvum* is considered to be one of the most important medicinal species, since it is utilised in various traditional medicinal system as an analgesic and anti-inflammatory agent (Ndebia *et al.*, 2007). It treats inflammatory diseases like fever, wounds and tooth decay. In rats, it relieves writhing and mechanical pain (Atta & Alkofahi, 1998; Ndebia *et al.*, 2007). The aqueous extracts of tannins and phenols exhibit anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties through several mechanisms. These include the inhibition of inflammatory mediators production, such as Prostaglandin and Cyclooxygenase, as well as the synthesis of Prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) via the arachidonic acid cascade, which plays a pivotal role in inflammatory mediation (Ndebia *et al.*, 2007).

The Carrageenan-induced rat paw oedema method was used to test *S. torvum* seed and fruit methanol extract for anti-inflammatory efficacy. All extracts had anti-inflammatory efficacy, but seed methanol extract at 500 mg/kg body weight was most effective (Rammohan & Reddy, 2010). At both the 300 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg doses of aqueous extract of *S. torvum* extract, paw oedema was considerably reduced; however, the 300 mg/kg dose was more rapid in its effect (Sridevi *et al.*, 2017; Yousaf *et al.*, 2013).

5. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Considering the escalating challenge of microbial resistance to the majority of antibiotics, medicinal plants are increasingly being explored as potential substitutes for the conventional treatment of many diseases (Chen *et al.*, 2005; Tanaka *et al.*, 2002). Six gram-positive and nine gram-negative human pathogenic bacteria were used to assess the antibacterial activity of *S. torvum* leaves, stems, roots and flowers that had been extracted using chloroform and methanol. When tested against bacteria, the methanolic extract from the roots was more effective than the extracts from the stems, leaves and flowers (Bari *et al.*, 2010).

Lalitha *et al.* (2010) documented the antibacterial efficacy of *S. torvum* leaf extract towards the seed-borne infections of rice utilizing aqueous and other

solvents including ethanol. The phytochemical components including, including terpenoids and phenolic compounds have antibacterial properties which could explain its antibacterial effect (Daglia, 2012; Neerja Gupta *et al.*, 2011).

The evaluation of the antimicrobial properties of the ethanolic extract derived from *S. torvum* fruits against six bacterial strains (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*) demonstrated noteworthy antibacterial efficacy against four of the analysed strains: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Jaabir *et al.*, 2015). Correlating to its phytochemical components, the ethanolic extract of *S. torvum* leaves has the ability to inhibit the growth of all pathogenic bacteria (Gram positive - *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, *S. intermedius* DMST 11465, *S. epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 11778 and Gram negative – *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 11778) tested (Naimon *et al.*, 2015). Sabarinath *et al.* (2018a) measured the inhibition zone diameter in plate culture to determine the *in vitro* effects of petroleum ether extracts from *S. torvum* leaves on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Proteus vulgaris* and concluded that the leaves possess antibacterial activity.

6. ANTICANCEROUS PROPERTY

The ethanolic extract of *S. torvum* berries showed effectiveness as an anticancer agent in an *in vitro* cytotoxicity study conducted by (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2014). Cytotoxicity percentages were measured for the extract at concentrations ranging from 50µg/ml to 1000µg/ml, with results ranging from 7.09% to 85.79%; which implies that the cytotoxicity effect was dose dependent. Balachandran *et al.* (2015) performed further experiments to investigate the anticancer effects of methyl caffeate isolated from fruit of *S. torvum*. The cytotoxic characteristics of hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol extract from the fruit were assessed against MCF7 cells utilising the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl

tetrazolium bromide assay. Ethyl acetate extract demonstrated superior cytotoxic activity as compared to hexane and methanol extracts. Methyl caffeate was extracted from ethyl acetate extract to examine its efficacy against MCF-7, A549, COLO320, HepG-2 and vero cells, demonstrating significant cytotoxic effects on MCF-7 cells.

Adenocarcinoma cell lines derived from the mammary gland showed remarkable resistance to cell proliferation when treated with *S. torvum* extracts. Phytochemicals such as Polyphenols, steroidal saponin glycoside, alkaloids and flavonoids play a pivotal part in *S. torvum*'s possible antioxidant activity, which in turn explains its strong antimitotic and anticancer effects (Thenmozhi & Rao, 2011). The research conducted by (Lai *et al.*, 2024) indicated that the ethanolic extract of *S. torvum* suppresses hepatoma cell proliferation by triggering ferroptosis. *S. torvum* had an additive impact with Lenvatinib in Hep 3B cells and demonstrated significant anti-HCC efficacy in Lenvatinib-resistant Hep 3B cells.

7. ANTIDIABETIC PROPERTY

A decoction of *S. torvum* fruits was used by the Yuan community of the northern Thailand to treat diabetes and hypertension (Inta *et al.*, 2013). The regeneration of β -cells in diabetic rats is linked to the phytochemicals and amino acids found in herbal plants (Apaya *et al.*, 2020). The findings of (Gandhi, Ignacimuthu, & Paulraj, 2011) showed that streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats' blood glucose levels were lowered by methanolic extract of *S. torvum* fruit containing phenolic compounds at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg. Additionally, it has been found to improve insulin secretion as a result of β -cell regeneration, decrease oxidative stress and regulate enzymes that are accountable for glucose metabolism. The inhibition of rat intestinal α -glucosidase (sucrase and maltase) was noted from *S. torvum* fruit extracts. Following enzyme-assay directed separation of the extract, methyl caffeate was identified as the inhibitor (Takahashi *et al.*, 2010). An anti-diabetic effect at doses of 10, 20 and 40 mg/kg of methyl caffeate, a chemical compound isolated from *S. torvum* fruit was

investigated. Methyl caffeate's effect on hyperglycemia in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats was dosage dependent and mediated by the up regulation of GLUT-4 and pancreatic β -cell regeneration (Gandhi, Ignacimuthu, Paulraj, *et al.*, 2011).

The analysis of pancreatic histopathology by ethanolic extract of *S. torvum* fruit has shown to regenerate β -cells in the Islet of Langerhans, perhaps leading to enhanced insulin output and hypoglycemia. Lower PCK1 gene expression may have lowered blood glucose in *S. torvum* fruit extract (200mg/kg)-treated rats. The activity of the phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase enzyme in the gluconeogenesis pathway is controlled by the PCK1 genes (Satyanarayana *et al.*, 2022).

At an oral dosage of 100 mg/kg, the methanolic extract of seeds of *S. torvum* showed promising antioxidant and antidiabetic effects. A high dose of 100 mg/kg of *S. torvum* methanolic extract had an impact comparable to that of 120 mg/kg of metformin, an oral hypoglycaemic agent (Mohan *et al.*, 2020).

8. HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

The availability of several phytoconstituents such as tannins, kaempferol, rutin, bergapten, psoralenes, flavonoids, coumarin and phenolic glycosides might explain the hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant benefits observed by (Tripathi, 2021).

After administering CCl₄ to albino rats, the hydroalcoholic extract of *S. torvum* fruits showed potential hepatoprotective effects at a dosage of 200 mg/kg on various biochemical parameters, including SGPT, SGOT, cholesterol, bilirubin, total protein and LDH (Kayalvizhi *et al.*, 2012). Diabetic rats developed using Streptozotocin and treated with *S. torvum* fruit extract exhibited reduced activity of ALT and AST enzymes, suggesting its hepatoprotective properties by preserving the functional integrity of the hepatic cell membrane and restoring impaired liver metabolism in diabetic rats (Mihailoviæ *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, a time dependent increase in AST and ALT levels was noted

in rats with diabetes induced by STZ (Abedimanesh *et al.*, 2021).

The evidence of hepatic injury by Streptozotocin was provided by an increase in liver enzyme activity and changes seen in the histological investigation of the liver. Treatment with the *S. torvum* methanolic extract showed a restorative effect in liver function, restoring hepatic damage to normal hepatocytes and considerably reducing high transaminase activity (Gandhi, Ignacimuthu, & Paulraj, 2011).

9. NEPHROPROTECTIVE PROPERTY

The phenolic compounds derived from the various forms of *S. torvum* and their nephroprotective effects were highlighted by (Loganayaki *et al.*, 2010). *S. torvum* treatment (100 mg/kg and 300 mg/kg) substantially reduced creatinine and BUN levels and enhanced SOD and CAT levels ($p < 0.05$). *S. torvum* alleviated tubular necrosis, renal lesions and glomerular congestion produced by DOX. The findings imply that *S. torvum* may reduce doxorubicin-induced nephrotoxicity (Mohan *et al.*, 2010). The two main renal measures are serum urea and creatinine. The body excretes urea and creatinine via urine. Renal dysfunction may reduce urea and creatinine clearance and cause their accumulation (Kim & Moon, 2012). Treatment with *S. torvum* extracts considerably enhanced the clearance of urea and creatinine, while the Monosodium Glutamate treated group showed a significant rise in serum urea and creatinine compared to control group, indicating renal insufficiency. Monosodium Glutamate induced histopathological alterations were reversed by *S. torvum* treatment (Kadam *et al.*, 2019).

The water extracts from the seeds of *S. torvum* have yielded novel proteins which, when compared to established synthetic standards, have potent nephron-protective effects at low concentrations (Darkwah *et al.*, 2020; Sivapriya & Leela, 2007a). The antioxidant capacity of the vitamins C and E found in *S. torvum* prevents molecules from oxidation or the loss of electrons which is the cause of their nephro-protective function. Their structural and chemical make-up actually makes it easy for them to stabilize oxidative molecules via electron

exchange. The nephro-protective potential of various vitamin C and E structures may be used to determine their efficacy (Darkwah *et al.*, 2020).

10. IMMUNOMODULATORY EFFECT

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) might be treated using the plant's immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties (Peranginangin *et al.*, 2013). *S. torvum*'s bioactive substances have a number of potential uses, including antimicrobial, antiviral and antifungal properties, along with immunomodulatory properties (Kannan *et al.*, 2012). The delayed type hypersensitivity (DTH) reaction, a direct correlate of cell mediated immunity (CMI), was markedly and dose-dependently amplified by the aqueous extract of *S. torvum*. Levamisole also had a comparable impact. The WBC count increased significantly ($p > 0.001$) in the extract and levamisole treated group compared to the dexamethasone and "No treatment" groups (Koffuor *et al.*, 2011b).

An elevation in the white blood cell and granulocytes count is one mechanism by which the aqueous extract of *S. torvum* exerts its immunomodulatory effects (Innih *et al.*, 2018; Israf *et al.*, 2004).

11. ANTIULCEROGENIC ACTIVITY

The fruits of *S. torvum* are used for treatment of ulcer (Noumi & Dibakto, 2000) and additionally the fruits are pulverized in hot water and then applied topically in Nigeria (Ajibesin *et al.*, 2008). Flavonoids, triterpenes and sterols found in *S. torvum* possess anti-ulcer properties by enhancing gastric mucosal defence (Antonio *et al.*, 2004; Nguelefack *et al.*, 2008; Télésphore B. *et al.*, 2008). According to the research conducted by (Télésphore B. *et al.*, 2008), rats' gastric mucosal lesions brought on by HCl/ethanol, indomethacin, pylorus ligation and cold-restraint stress are significantly inhibited by the aqueous and methanolic extract of *S. torvum* leaves and an increase in mucus production, which in turn strengthens the mucosal barrier, which maybe the cause of the cytoprotective activity. The anti-ulcer activities of *S. torvum* flavonoid derivatives are achieved by increasing mucus production and neutralising the acidic content (Mendes *et al.*, 2012).

CONCLUSION

Since the beginning of time, people have turned to herbs as a source of medicine for a wide range of illnesses. One of the most significant angiosperm families in terms of both commercial and therapeutic significance is the Solanaceae family. *Solanum torvum* belonging to family solanaceae is a small shrub and is found widely in India, China, Pakistan, Philippines, Malaya and tropical America. The plant's dried stem and root have been utilized for decades by numerous ethnic groups to treat a variety of diseases.

The synthesis of several phytochemicals by *S. torvum* explains the widespread traditional therapeutic usage. According to reports, *S. torvum* contains a variety of phytochemicals including proteins, amino acids, oils, tocopherols, glycosides, alkaloids, phenols, tannins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, steroids and glycosides.

The rich phytochemical concentration attributes to varied pharmacological benefits. The various parts of plants are used to tackle illnesses such as cough, enlarged spleen, heart problems and pain. It is also effectively used for its antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancerous, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, immunomodulatory and antiulcerogenic activities. Its significance in both traditional and alternative medicine as well as the presence of a number of chemicals with medicinal potential warrant more investigation into its effect.

There are many interesting and unidentified medicinal plants, some of which are already used clinically in medicinal formulations. Thus, Ayurvedic drugs must be reviewed for the therapeutic efficacy and standardized by chemical and biochemical assay to ensure active principal consistency in each dose.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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